

Machine Learning-Enhanced Indoor Positioning Using Photovoltaic Cells for Light-Based Internet of Things

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Abstract

The development of 6G technology is driving the development of sustainable Internet of Things (IoT)-based sensor networks, emphasising low-cost and environmentally friendly solutions. Light-based IoT (LIoT) emerges as a promising approach, leveraging the unlicensed optical spectrum for energy autonomy through photovoltaic energy harvesting and Visible Light Communication (VLC) via indoor luminaires acting as Optical Access Points (OAPs). This research explores integrating Machine Learning (ML) techniques for indoor positioning within LIoT sensor networks, supporting the intermittent, energy-autonomous operation. We propose an ML-based indoor positioning method that utilises OAPs for data preprocessing and model training, capitalising on existing energy harvesters (EH) for both power generation and position detection. A proof-of-concept LIoT node prototype was developed and tested against conventional supervised ML algorithms. Results demonstrate that these ML models can achieve distance accuracy with error margins within 7 cm and positioning accuracy within 20 cm. This study highlights the design approaches and potential of integrating EH systems with ML-based positioning. By enabling indoor location detection, this integration allows LIoT-based devices to communicate, harvest energy, and acknowledge their position using the same illumination from OAPs.

Visible light communication, Indoor positioning, Battery-free IoT, Sustainable IoT

1 Introduction

Sustainable Internet of Things (IoT)-based sensor networks are gaining significant interest with the development of 6G networks [1]. Due to their

low environmental impact, sustainable, low-cost, and low-complexity IoT technologies are increasingly being adopted across a wide range of everyday applications. These technologies can be seamlessly integrated into systems such as sensing devices for logistics, healthcare, industrial automation, and environmental monitoring. The concept of Light-based Internet of Things (LIoT) promotes sustainability by utilising the unlicensed optical spectrum, enabling battery-free energy autonomy, and employing less complex, environmentally friendly, and sustainable electronic technologies [2, 3]. Since LIoT devices are designed to communicate and self-power using Optical Access Point (OAP) based Visible Light Communication (VLC) and Photovoltaic (PV) Energy Harvesting (EH), these nodes are equipped with integrated photodetectors and energy harvesters such as PV cells. The reuse of energy harvesters for dual purposes, such as sensors, is discussed under the concept of "Energy Harvesters as a Sensor" (EHAAS) [4]. While indoor positioning using VLC has been explored in previous research, some studies have also discussed the use of PV cells in the EH units of battery-powered IoT nodes for indoor positioning purposes [5]. Therefore, it is worthwhile to investigate the feasibility of integrating this concept into energy-autonomous nodes, such as LIoT, which operate intermittently due to constrained energy availability. Incorporating indoor localisation capabilities into LIoT nodes could significantly enhance the functionality and usability of such networks.

The application of machine learning for indoor positioning has been widely explored by researchers. Supervised learning models, including Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), decision trees, random forests, and Support Vector Machines (SVM), are particularly effective in enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of Visible Light Positioning (VLP) systems. These models improve accuracy, reduce computational time, and increase system stability un-

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Figure 1: System model

der varying lighting conditions, thereby meeting the real-time requirements of practical applications. In VLP systems, Received Signal Strength (RSS)-based fingerprinting is typically used to generate the necessary training and testing datasets for implementing these models [6, 7]. Recent advancements in energy-efficient edge-based ML models have enabled lightweight ML inference directly on devices, opening up a range of applications in low-power environments [8]. This approach can be particularly applicable for power-constrained IoT devices to estimate VLP at the node level.

This research proposes an ML-based indoor positioning approach for intermittently operating, energy-autonomous LLoT nodes. The approach utilises an OAP for data preprocessing and ML model training, making it well-suited for OAP-centralised, power-constrained LLoT nodes. In this work, we explore LLoT node design strategies that re-purpose energy harvesters for indoor positioning determination. Based on these strategies, we developed a proof-of-concept prototype. Our results demonstrate that conventional machine learning models can achieve acceptable positioning accuracy in LLoT environments.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: Section II discusses the model of the proposed system. Section III describes the implemented prototype system for evaluation. Finally, Section IV presents the performance evaluation and discussion, followed by conclusions.

2 System Model

A scenario where the proposed LLoT positioning approach can be illustrated as in Figure 1.

In a typical LLoT sensor network setup, illumination sources are expected to function as OAP, while nodes are expected to transmit information via optical up-link, typically using infrared [2, 3]. Since integrated PV cells are the sole energy generators for LLoT, incorporating them in an omnidirectional arrangement can enhance EH from reflections and further mitigate the effects of orientation-induced illumination shadowing in various application scenarios. However, in typical indoor illumination arrangements, only a few of these integrated PV cells will receive full illumination, while the PV cells facing away from the light source will experience low illumination conditions. As shown in Figure 1, PV-integrated surfaces 3, 4, and 5 of node 1 and surfaces 3, 2, and 5 of node 2 are well illuminated. In contrast, PV surfaces 1 and 2 of Node 1 are not illuminated, while surfaces 1 and 4 of node 2 receive slight illumination due to reflected light from nearby surfaces. Generally, the variation of open circuit voltage of PV cell with light intensity can be given by following equation [9].

$$V_{OC} = \frac{nkT}{q} \ln(I) + C \quad (1)$$

where V_{OC} is the open-circuit voltage, k is the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature, q is the elementary charge, n is the ideality factor, I is the intensity, and C is a fitting parameter. Therefore, it can be expressed as the voltage on differently illuminated PV surfaces as:

$$V_{DI} > V_{SI} > V_{NI} \quad (2)$$

where V_{DI} represents the voltage on well-illuminated PV surfaces, V_{SI} represents the voltage on slightly illuminated PV surfaces, and V_{NI} represents the voltage on non-illuminated PV surfaces.

Based on 2, it can be seen that the direction of the illumination source can be estimated from the voltage generated on the surface. This will be useful for determining the direction of the OAP location relative to the current orientation of the LLoT node. The received optical power can be defined P_r is given by [10]:

$$P_r = (H_{los}(0) + H_{nlos}(0)) P_t \quad (3)$$

where P_t is the transmitted power, $H_{los}(0)$ is the channel gain for the line-of-sight component, and $H_{nlos}(0)$ is the channel gain for the non-line-of-sight components.

The channel gains for the line-of-sight (LOS) and non-line-of-sight (NLOS) components in an optical wireless communication system are given by the following equations:

The channel gain for the LOS component, H_{LOS} ,

Figure 2: Proposed structure for LIoT positioning enabled node

is given by:

$$H_{LOS} = \frac{n+1}{2\pi} \frac{A}{d^2} \rho \cos^n(\phi_d) T_s(\psi_d) g(\psi_d) \cos(\psi) \quad (4)$$

where n is the order of Lambertian emission, A is the receiver aperture area, d is the distance between the transmitter and receiver, ρ is the reflectance, ϕ_d is the irradiance angle, $T_s(\psi_d)$ is the gain of the optical filter, $g(\psi_d)$ is the gain of the optical concentrator, and ψ is the angle of incidence.

The channel gain for the NLOS component, H_{NLOS} , is given by: $rCl H_{NLOS} = \frac{n+1}{2\pi} \frac{A}{d^2} \rho \cos^n(\phi_r) d_{ref} \cos(\lambda) \cos(\gamma) \times T_s(\psi_d) g(\psi_d) \cos(\psi_r)$ where ϕ_r is the irradiance angle for the NLOS path, d_{ref} is the distance of the reflected path, λ is the angle related to the reflection, γ is the angle related to the incident direction on the reflecting surface, and ψ_r is the angle of incidence for the NLOS path.

As demonstrated by both equations 4 and 2, the receiving optical power decreases with increased distance. Hence, this principle can be applied to determine the distance of a node by measuring the received illumination intensity, which corresponds to the PV cell voltage. Therefore, by transmitting these voltage measurements to the power-unrestricted OAP via a data uplink, indoor LIoT location estimation calculations can be performed. Based on the illumination variation on the node's surfaces, measured using the existing PV cells in the energy harvesting units, localisation information for the LIoT nodes can be determined.

2.1 Proposed structure of the node and OAP

The proposed LIoT node structure for PV-based positioning capabilities can be illustrated as shown in Figure 2. Similar to a typical LIoT node structure, it includes power management to drive PV cells around the maximum power point and efficiently transfer the harvested energy to storage [3]. The Micro-Controller Unit (MCU) is powered by the DC output of the power management, while the optical transceiver and sensor circuits are powered

by and communicate with the MCU. In addition, a switching circuit is utilised to connect individual different PV cell probes for measurement purposes with minimal disruption to the energy harvesting operation of the Energy Harvesting Unit (EHU). The switching circuit unit is also designed to down-convert the voltage levels to be compatible with the MCU Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) measurement, ensuring that this process has minimal or no impact on the EH operation.

The OAP needs to be designed to facilitate data modulation while ensuring flicker-free, indoor-friendly lighting. This system necessitates an LED driver that can control the connected LEDs to illuminate according to the data signal. Additionally, the OAP processor needs to analyse information received from LIoT nodes in the cluster, such as PV voltage values, to determine locations. This process demands sufficient computational power from the OAP processor.

2.2 Machine learning at OAP

Research into energy-efficient edge-based ML models has enabled lightweight models to be used for on-device ML inference for various applications. An ML model can significantly enhance LIoT positioning accuracy and speed of position calculation. Based on the readings from multiple PV cells at the LIoT node, which corresponds to its location, the ML model at the OAP can proceed with inference and calculate the precise location of the LIoT node. Taking into account the battery-less LIoT nodes, which have power constraints and an intermittent operation nature, the OAP could be utilised to perform data preprocessing and ML model training. Nowadays, due to the advancements of TinyML frameworks, it gets easier to enable ML models in the embedded hardware. It is proposed that traditional ML models can achieve acceptable levels of performance in terms of LIoT positioning accuracy. The ML models considered in this research are described below.

2.2.1 Linear regression (LR)

LR is a fundamental approach in statistics and machine learning that models the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables. In its simplest form, it uses a straight line, described by the equation $y = mx + b$, where m is the slope and b is the intercept, to predict the dependent variable y based on the independent variable x . Linear regression is widely used in predictive modeling to forecast continuous outcomes. It also serves as a basis for more advanced techniques like ridge regression and Lasso, which incorporate regularisation to address multicollinearity and prevent over-fitting. Although linear regression assumes a

linear relationship between variables, which may not always hold, it remains a powerful and popular method in both classical statistics and modern machine learning due to its simplicity and interpretability [11].

2.2.2 Support Vector Machine (SVM)

SVM is a geometric-based classification algorithm. The primary goal of an SVM is to establish an optimal boundary, known as a hyperplane, that effectively partitions the space into distinct categories. SVMs can be categorized into two main types: linear SVMs, where data points are separated by a straight line, and nonlinear SVMs, which use nonlinear boundaries to divide the data points [12].

2.2.3 Decision Trees (DT)

In a DT, each internal node represents a test on an attribute, and each branch is an outcome of the test. The leaf nodes represent a class label. The process begins at the root node, where the algorithm checks the attribute specified by that node. Based on the value of this attribute, the algorithm follows the corresponding branch to the next node. This process is repeated, moving down the tree and checking attributes at each node, until a leaf node is reached. The leaf node represents the final classification decision for the instance [11].

2.2.4 Random Forest (RF)

The RF is an ensemble classification algorithm that employs a technique known as "parallel ensembling." In this approach, multiple decision tree classifiers are trained simultaneously on different sub-samples of the dataset. The final outcome is determined by majority voting or by averaging the results of these trees. This method helps to minimise the problem of overfitting while enhancing both prediction accuracy and model robustness [11].

3 Prototype Implementation

To measure the performance of the proposed indoor positioning concept, a proof-of-concept OAP and LIoT prototype node were developed. The prototype designed was entirely based on suggested design methodologies from previous research works [2,3]. The finalised node incorporated five surfaces, to which five PV cells were embedded, thereby enhancing its energy harvesting and localisation performance. The picture of prototype node is given in Figure 3

Figure 3: Proof of concept prototype LIoT node.

Figure 4: Prototype OAP schematic

3.1 OAP and LIoT node implementation

The schematic of the implemented prototype OAP is shown in Figure 4. This prototype OAP used two separate Arduino nano development boards for transmitting and receiving signals from the deployed LIoT nodes. Multiple KY-002 IR receiver modules were employed to detect the incoming IR signals within the uplink communication between the nodes and the OAP. An IRF520 MOSFET module drove the white LED array, maintaining flicker-free illumination. The data received from the 2nd Arduino nano board was forwarded to a connected computer for data capture and analysis. A 12W LED table lamp with a swivel arm was used as the illumination source.

Figure 5 illustrates the schematic of the LIoT prototype implemented for the experiment. The node is based on an Arduino Pro-Mini 3.3V 8MHz board with the indicator LED and power regulators disconnected. For the EHU, an Epishine EK01LEH3-6 module was utilised, comprising an AEM10941 with Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) operation, a CAP-XX GA230F 0.4F super-capacitor for energy storage, and a TPS62740 DC-DC converter output. The node employed a TMP36GT9Z temperature sensor as its primary sensing element. The prototype node incorporated five Epishine LEH3-50x50-6-10 printed organic PV cells, one for each surface. In order to enhance multi-directional com-

Figure 5: Proof of concept positioning capable LLoT prototype node schematic

Figure 6: PV probe switching circuit

munication, the up-link utilised four PCB0100 dual-channel infrared transmitter modules. The PV switching circuit employed five MOSFETs, each paired with a voltage divider circuit. Upon receiving a Transistor-Transistor Logic (TTL) HIGH voltage signal at the MOSFET gate terminal, the circuit connects the associated PV cell terminal to the MCU for ADC measurement. Conversely, when the applied gate voltage is TTL LOW, the MOSFET disconnects the voltage divider, preserving the PV cell voltage and minimising any disruption to the energy harvesting process.

3.2 OAP and LLoT node algorithm

The algorithm for the OAP follows a similar approach as in previous work [2]. Based on sensor data or location information requests, it generates commands for the LLoT node and transmits them using the transmitter core via the Infrared (IR) protocols. The receiver core waits for any incoming data from the optical channel. Once a signal is detected, the receiver checks the bit length and then proceeds to decode the information. The simplified prototype node algorithm is illustrated in Figure 7. This algorithm is designed to be energy-aware. To achieve this, internal super-capacitor voltage measurements are utilised. When the voltage levels approach the minimum threshold for the DC-DC converter in the EHU, they are considered as indicating the mini-

Figure 7: Prototype LLoT node energy aware algorithm

imum energy level. Conversely, when the voltage is near the maximum level set by the power management unit for storage, it is considered to represent the maximum energy level. The node, therefore, operates intermittently, following the developed algorithm.

3.3 ML-based positioning approach

In this work, four well-known supervised ML classification algorithms, previously discussed, were employed: LR, SVM, DT, and RF. In supervised learning, a set of training data S is used to train the algorithm, while a separate dataset, called the testing database S' , is utilised to assess the performance of the trained classifier. The assessment involves comparing the predicted results P' provided by the classifier for each input vector in the testing database with the actual values P . The objective of this work is not to propose a new localisation method, but rather to utilise established classification algorithms.

In order to evaluate and compare the performance of the ML models, we used the Euclidean distance metric. The Euclidean distance between two points i and j in an M -dimensional space is given by the equation:

$$d_{i,j} = \sqrt{\sum_{m=1}^M (p_{m,i}^{on} - P_{m,j})^2} \quad (5)$$

where, $p_{m,i}^{on}$ and $P_{m,j}$ are the coordinates of points i and j in the m -th dimension, respectively [6]. This distance metric provided a straightforward way to assess how accurately the ML models could predict the positions of the measurement points relative to the known centre of the OAP.

The selection of the ML models was guided by the introduction of a tolerance metric, ϵ , which quantifies the numerical error between the predicted po-

Figure 8: View of experiemnt setup

Figure 9: Illumination (Lux value) distribution over the test grid.

sition P' and the actual position P . The tolerance metric is defined as:

$$\epsilon = |P - P'| \quad (6)$$

The suitability of the ML models can be compared based on ϵ .

4 Performance evaluation

For the performance evaluation, the LIoT Node prototype was placed at various locations on an 8x14 grid, with each position spaced 10x10 cm apart. The total area of the test grid is 0.8 x 1.4m. The OAP was mounted 0.6 meters above the test grid and positioned asymmetrically to create areas with varying surface reflections. At each location, the prototype LIoT node operated energy autonomously, powered by the OAP's illumination, and transmitted PV voltage data from each surface along with sensor readings. Consequently, all PV surface voltages obtained were measured while the node's EHU was functioning. The layout of the experiment setup is in Figure 8. The illumination distribution was measured using a CA 1110 lux-meter, and the corresponding grid arrangement is shown in Figure 9.

At each designated location on the test grid, the prototype node was rotated, and four readings were taken. The surface voltage variation, based on the average value of these readings, is illustrated in Fig-

Average Surface PV Cell Voltage Variation

Figure 10: Average surface voltage variation for each position at the test grid.

ure 10. This dataset was utilised in the OAP to determine the node's location.

4.1 Prototype Node performance

Similar to the previous work, the data link successfully achieved a transfer rate of 1.4 Kbps, which was sufficient for transmitting the PV and sensor data upon request. The node's minimum sleep power consumption was 0.08 mW, while it consumed 0.8 mW during idle listening.

4.2 ML model selection

Before starting the training process of the ML model, we first performed data preprocessing to ensure the input data was suitable for model training. This preprocessing included several important steps:

4.2.1 Aggregation of Data

We calculated the average PV cell values for each measurement, which helped to reduce noise and variability in the data, leading to more stable and representative features for the ML model.

4.2.2 Normalisation of PV Cell Values

To ensure that the PV cell values were on a comparable scale, we normalised them using the Min-Max normalisation technique. This method scales the data so that it falls within a specific range, typically $[0, 1]$, as described by (7). This step is crucial because it helps the ML model to converge more efficiently during training by preventing features with larger ranges from dominating those with smaller ranges.

$$x' = \frac{x - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)} \quad (7)$$

4.2.3 Conversion of Position Labels

The position labels, which were originally represented alphabetically along the x-axis, were converted into numerical values. We did this by assigning a numerical value to each alphabetical label and incrementing the x-axis values by 10 cm for each successive label. This conversion allowed us to treat the position labels as numerical features, which are necessary for most ML models.

The dataset split used for the ML models training was as follows: 80% of the PV cell values,

$$S = \{PV_1, PV_2, PV_3, PV_4, PV_5\}, \quad (8)$$

were used to train the algorithm, while the remaining 20% of the PV cell values, designated as the testing database S' , were used for model evaluation. The centre of the OAP location was at coordinates $(45, 45)$, and using (5) the distance d_i between the center point and each position was calculated, where d_i values were used as labels.

For evaluation, SVM with a radial basis function kernel was used, which splits the feature space into disjoint regions using hyper-planes. Each disjoint region, bounded by these hyper-planes, corresponds to a mapped room present in the training database. For the DT, a binary-tree representation was employed, where each internal node represents a true/false test on the voltage intensity of a particular PV cell. If the intensity level exceeds a certain threshold, the true branch of the binary tree is followed to the next node, with each leaf node corresponding to a mapped room in the training database. Finally, the RF algorithm was configured with an ensemble of 100 trees, a parameter empirically shown to provide good results for this specific training data. Similar to the DT, each leaf node in the Random Forest corresponds to a mapped room in the training database. Fig.(11) depicts the comparison of ML models' prediction accuracy of the distance from LIoT node to the OAP.

Figure 11: The ML models accuracy vs tolerance

Figure 12: The ML models MSE vs tolerance

To evaluate the selected ML performance, we used Mean Square Error (MSE) as an evaluation metric (9). Fig.12 shows, that RF model showed the lowest average MSE, indicating it performed the best overall across different tolerance values. DT follows closely and performs well, but LR and SVM models have higher MSE values, suggesting they were less accurate.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (d_i - \hat{d}_i)^2 \quad (9)$$

We can observe, that the RF outperforms the rest of the models and achieves more than 80% accuracy at the tolerance of 7cm distance to the light source prediction. Based on these results we decided to use the Random Forest model to perform positioning of the prototype LIoT node.

4.3 ML model performance

The ML model performance was evaluated first by selecting RF to do the position prediction. As a

Figure 13: The Random Forest accuracy vs tolerance

previous method, we used tolerance versus accuracy as an evaluation metric.

Figure 13 shows that the selected RF regression model achieves 80% prediction accuracy when a tolerance level of more than 20 cm is applied. This indicates that the model can correctly predict the node’s position within a 20 cm margin of error in 80% of the cases. While this accuracy is notable, the tolerance level also reflects some variation in the model’s predictions. A tolerance of over 7 cm suggests that the model is generally effective at estimating the distance to the OAP’s center point, though there is some margin of error in predicting the exact position of the node. In other words, the RF model provides a reliable estimate of distance, but its precision in position measurements may vary. This variation could be due to several factors, such as the complexity of the environment, the limitations of the input features, or the inherent noise in the data. Therefore, depending on the specific requirements of the LIoT application, the model’s performance at different tolerance levels should be carefully considered.

Discussion

This paper proposes an ML-based indoor positioning approach for LIoT sensor networks. The existing PV energy harvesters in the harvesting unit are repurposed to obtain positioning information. The approach leverages the unconstrained power availability at the light source, which acts as an OAP, to perform ML-based position computation. Meanwhile, the LIoT nodes maintain their characteristic intermittent operation, transmitting the necessary PV cell voltage values to the OAP intermittently. To demonstrate the feasibility of this approach, a proof-of-concept LIoT node was developed, and the

required design strategies were discussed. Based on the generated dataset of PV cell voltage readings, we demonstrate that node positioning can be achieved with satisfactory accuracy by employing conventional machine-learning models. Specifically, using the Random Forest regression model, we observed an error margin of at least 20 cm and a distance margin of 7 cm. This level of accuracy is sufficient for certain LIoT-integrated applications. The accuracy of the errors could be influenced by the surface characteristics of the test grid, such as its reflectivity, as well as the construction material of the node. In our case, the node was made of transparent material, which allows light to partially pass through to other surfaces. Additionally, the low indoor illumination-optimised OPV cells used in the experiment tend to reach their maximum possible voltages even with slight illumination. Consequently, the accuracy could be affected when the prototype node is located in areas with moderate illumination. As a precaution, multiple small PV cells could be integrated into each PV interface, rather than using a single cell. As a future direction, we suggest that using neural networks, particularly tailored Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) models, could potentially surpass the performance of the models selected in this study. Additionally, improved designs of PV voltage probes could further enhance positioning accuracy. Exploring methodologies for highly illuminated multi-OAP LIoT systems, where both position and node orientation can be identified, is another promising avenue. This positioning awareness in LIoT nodes can significantly enhance their functionality, enabling them to communicate, energise, and maintain location awareness based on existing indoor illumination.

Conclusion

This study introduces an ML-based approach for indoor positioning within LIoT sensor networks. By repurposing existing PV EH, the approach effectively leverages continuous energy harvesting while providing location-related illumination information for ML calculations with acceptable accuracy. Our proof-of-concept work demonstrates that, using Random Forest regression, node positioning can be achieved with an error margin as low as 20 cm and a distance margin of 7 cm, which is applicable for certain LIoT applications where such accuracy is sufficient. Moreover, the study confirms that EH-powered, battery-less nodes can utilise their PV cell voltage readings for positioning with satisfactory accuracy when employing conventional ML models. Ultimately, this positioning awareness could significantly enhance the efficiency, effectiveness, and sustainability of LIoT networks, fostering new applications where communication,

energy harvesting, and location awareness are seamlessly integrated.

Acknowledgment

This research was supported by the SUPERIOT and Greenedge project. The SUPERIOT project has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101096021, including top-up funding by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee. The Greenedge project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska Curie Innovative Training Network Greenedge (GA.No. 953775).

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